

**Comparative Study Of Silver Coated Urinary Catheter Vs Conventional Latex
Catheter In Prevention Of Catheter Associated Urinary Tract Infection**

by

DR.HANUMATH AMMANNA

Dissertation submitted to

In partial fulfillment for the degree of

MASTER OF SURGERY

IN

GENERAL SURGERY

Under the guidance of

DR TEJASWINI V. M.S.(SURG)

PROFESSOR

DEPARTMENT OF GENERAL SURGERY

BLDE (DEEMED TO BE UNIVERSITY)

SHRI B. M. PATILMEDICAL COLLEGE, HOSPITAL & RESEARCH CENTRE

VIJAYAPUR – 586103

2019

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

HAI	Hospital Acquired Infections
CDC	Centre For Disease Control and Prevention
CAUTI	Catheter Associated Urinary Tract Infection
cfu	colony forming unit
UTI	Urinary Tract Infection
Fr	French Unit for Measurement; 1 Fr = 0.33 mm
PVC	Poly Vinyl Chloride
CIC	Clean Intermittent Catheterization
PTFE	Polytetrafluoroethylene
EAU	European Association Urology
IDSA	Infectious Disease Society of America
INICC	International Nosocomial Infection Control Consortium
BMI	Body Mass Index
AUA	American Urological Association
SSD	Silver Sulphadiazine
VAP	Ventilator Associated Pneumonia
AgO	Silver Oxide

ABSTRACT

AIMS & OBJECTIVES

Comparative study of silver coated urinary catheter vs conventional latex catheter in prevention of catheter associated urinary tract infection

MATERIALS AND METHODS-

Out of 240, 120 patients were treated with silver oxide coated Foley's catheter and 120 patients with conventional Foley's after baseline urine culture was found to be sterile and between age group 18- 89 yrs were included in the study. Patients with pre-existing UTI and urogenital abnormality were excluded from the study. The urine analysis and culture for bacterial count was assessed on day 1, day 3 and day7 or more and the results were compared.

RESULTS- in our study, we found that the mean age between the statistically not significant. Out of 240 study sample, 140 (59 %) were males and 99 (41 %) were females. On comparing the urine for pus cells, it was observed that there was significant decrease in the number of patients with positive urine for pus cells when there was an indwelling catheter for 7 days or more. It was also seen that the most common organism isolated was Escherichia. Coli, followed by Staphylococcus Aureus, Klebsiella Pneumonia, Pseudomonas species, and others.

CONCLUSION- In our study, there was no statistical difference in distribution of patients between the study group and control group with respect to age and sex.

Urine examination for evidence of pus cells was found significantly low in the study group on the Day 7 or more (up to 14 days) of urinary tract catheterization with P value – 0.027, whereas there was no difference on the incidence at the end of Day1 or Day3. Thus, we can infer from the above results that the Silver Oxide impregnated Foley's catheter was efficacious in reducing the occurrence of Catheter related urinary tract infections.

It was observed from our study that the Silver Oxide impregnation to plain Foleys catheter has the potential to prevent/reduce the incidence of catheter associated urinary tract infections in patients who need longer duration of catheterization for various reasons. It was also observed in our study that duration of study was a significant risk factor in predisposing a patient to infections.

CONTENTS

SL. NO.	TOPIC	PAGE NO.
1	INTRODUCTION	1
2	AIM AND OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY	6
3	RESEARCH HYPOTHESIS	7
4	REVIEW OF LITERATURE	8
5	MATERIALS AND METHODS	25
6	RESULTS	32
7	DISCUSSION	43
8	CONCLUSION	47
9	SUMMARY	48
10	BIBLIOGRAPHY	49
11	ANNEXURE I – ETHICAL CLEARANCE CERTIFICATE	56
12	ANNEXURE II – CONSENT FORM	57
13	ANNEXURE III – PROFORMA	62

LIST OF TABLES

SL. NO.	DESCRIPTION	PAGE NO.
1	CATHETER SIZE BASED ON AGE	12
2	DISTRIBUTION OF PATIENTS ACCORDING TO AGE IN STUDY AND CONTROL GROUP	32
3	DISTRIBUTION OF PATIENTS ACCORDING TO GENDER IN STUDY AND CONTROL	33
4	MEAN AGE BETWEEN STUDY AND CONTROL GROUP	34
5	COMPARISON OF BMI BETWEEN STUDY AND CONTROL GROUP	35
6	INDICATIONS FOR CATHETERIZATION	35
7	COMPARISON OF URINE FOR PUS CELLS IN PATIENTS BETWEEN STUDY AND CONTROL	38
8	COMPARISON OF URINE CULTURE BETWEEN STUDY AND CONTROL GROUP	39
9	COMPARISON SYMPTOMATIC CAUTI BETWEEN STUDY AND CONTROL GROUP	42

LIST OF FIGURES

SL. NO.	DESCRIPTION	PAGE NO.
1	Course of Male Urethra.	10
2	Course of Female Urethra.	11
3	Three-way, Two- way and Single lumen catheter.	14
4	Classical two- way Foley's catheter.	27
5	Temperature Controlled Water Bath.	29
6	Ethylene Oxide Sterilizer.	29
7	Commercially available conventional Foley 's catheter.	30
8	Silver Oxide impregnated Foley's catheter.	30
9	Distribution of patients according to Age in study and control group.	32
10	Distribution of patients according to Gender in study and control group.	34
11	Indications for catheterization in Study Group	38
12	Indications for catheterization in Control Group	38
13	Comparison of urine for pus cells in patients between study and control group.	39
14	Organisms isolated in Study group.	41
15	Organisms isolated in Control group.	41
16	Comparison symptomatic CAUTI between study and control group.	42

1. INTRODUCTION

Hospital-acquired infections (HAI) also known as health-care related infections are nosocomially (originating or taking place in a health care facility) acquired infections that occur up to 48 hours after hospital admission or up to 3 days after discharge or up to 30 days after an operation or in a healthcare facility when someone is admitted for reasons other than the infection¹.

About 1 in 10 people who are admitted to a hospital for any reason will develop a nosocomial infection. These healthcare-related infections include central line-associated bloodstream infections, catheter-associated urinary tract infections, and ventilator-associated pneumonia and surgical site infections¹. These are potentially preventable infections which are under the surveillance of International Nosocomial Infection Control Consortium (INICC), which was founded in 1998. In developed countries nosocomial infections account for 7 % percent of the hospitalized patients and in developing nations, they account for 10 % percent. During hospital stay, these infections cause extended stay, disability and financial burden. Nosocomial pathogens include bacteria, viruses and fungal parasites. Pneumonia (21.8%) and surgical site infections (21.8%) are the leading causes, followed by gastrointestinal infections (17.1%), urinary tract infection (12.9%) and primary bloodstream infection (9.9%)².

“The Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC) defines Catheter Associated Urinary Tract Infection (CAUTI) for those patients who have an indwelling catheter in place for 48 h or more with symptoms such as fever or chills, new onset of burning pain, urgency or frequency, change in urine character, flank or suprapubic pain or tenderness or change or decrease in mental or functional status in patients”. Diagnosis of CAUTI is considered when there is presence of at least 10^3 colony-forming units cfu / ml of 1 or 2

micro-organisms by urine culture³.

Urinary tract infections are the most prevalent form of Hospital Acquired Infection (HAI), accounting for over 30 percent of acute care hospital-reported diseases³. Virtually all health -care associated UTIs are caused by instrumentation of the urinary tract, which accounts approximately for about 80 %⁴. It leads to prolonged hospitalization and increased cost of treatment. It is seen that some of the causative agents are multi-drug resistant micro-organisms thus making it difficult to treat. The mortality rate of UTI following urinary catheterization is less than 5%⁴.

Although number of bladder catheters inserted each year is more than 30 million, at least 6 times higher than the number of central venous catheters, catheter-associated UTI is the second most common cause of nosocomial bloodstream infection⁵.

Although an indwelling intravascular and urinary catheter are key components of modern medical care, they significantly increase the risk of iatrogenic infection, particularly in the already fragile patient population. The risk of developing bacteriuria in a patient with an indwelling catheter is approximately 3% to 10% / day. Among them, 10 to 25 % develop symptoms of local infection and about 1 to 4 % develop bacteremia⁶. Various studies emphasize that even if other co-morbidities are taken care of, there is three times increase in mortality and morbidity associated with urinary catheter related infections⁷.

In order to reduce the burden of catheter associated infections, various types of catheter coatings have been implemented. The word “catheter” comes from Greek, meaning “to let or send down.” Using catheters was known as early as 3,000 B.C. to alleviate painful retention of urine. In those times, many materials were used to form a hollow catheter shape, including straw, rolled up palm leaves, hollow tops of onions, as well as, gold, silver, copper, brass, and lead⁸.

In the 11th century, malleable catheters were created. In time, silver was used as the basis of catheters as it could be bent to any required form and was felt to have an antimicrobial function⁹. In 18th century Benjamin Franklin, the inventor and colonial statesman, designed silver catheters to be used in his elder brother John, who was suffering from kidney stones and had to undergo a daily ritual of placing a bulky metal catheter into his bladder. To make this less painful, he worked with a local silversmith on his design for a flexible catheter. "It is as flexible as would be expected in a thing of the kind, and I imagine will readily comply with the turns of the passage," he wrote to John. To allow drainage, holes were bored into the sides of the catheter¹⁰.

Coudé tip catheters were created in the 18th and 19th centuries to facilitate male catheterization and are in use for this purpose in current medical practice. Catheters made from rubber were introduced in the 18th century but were weak at body temperature, leaving debris in the bladder. With the introduction of rubber vulcanization by Goodyear in 1844 lead to increase in catheter's firmness and durability, encouraging mass production. In the 1930s, latex rubber was introduced into clinical practice¹¹. Dr. Frederic E.B. Foley (a St. Paul urologist) introduced the latex balloon catheter at a urologic meeting in 1935. Though he lost a legal battle with Davol for the patent, this catheter has since been known as the "Foley". The earliest self-retaining catheters had wing tips (known as Malecot) or flexible shoulders (known as Pezzer), attached to the male penis or sutured to the female labia¹¹. The French scale of Charriere was used to define a catheter's internal diameter.

Thus, the term "French (Fr)" size was coined. Joseph-Frederic-Benoit Charriere was a 19th century Parisian maker of surgical instruments. A 12 French catheter is approximately 4 mm in external diameter (0.33 mm = 1 French [Fr]). Sir Ludwig Guttman introduced the idea of sterile intermittent catheterization in patients with spinal cord injury after World War II. Sterile method has been used for catheterization for many years since then. In 1971,

the clean intermittent catheterization method was initiated by Dr. Jack Lapides of Michigan University at Ann Arbor. Dr. Lapides believed that bacteria were not the only cause of infection. He thought that it was also because of chronic stagnant urine residuals and overdistention of the bladder¹².

Silver ion is known to have bactericidal effects and biocompatibility and is used as topical agent in other situations like burns wounds. Following impregnation of silver on catheters, there is migration of silver ions which has antimicrobial effects and is not toxic to patients⁴.

Antibiotic coatings have been tried on catheters but its benefit is questionable as these remains risk of antibiotic resistance¹³.

Since early 1990s, research has focused on different anti-infective catheter-coating materials but results have been generally inconclusive. Bactiguard-coated Foley catheters, an essential noble metal (gold, silver, and palladium) alloy and hydrogel-coated catheter, have been introduced to slow bacterial colonisation. In the early 2000s, a randomised cross-over study by Karchmer et al¹³ demonstrated that the risk of UTI could be decreased by 21% in wards when a noble metal alloy catheter was used instead of a conventional catheter. Since then, more studies to compare anti-infective urinary catheters with conventional urinary catheters have been carried out. The noble metal alloy indwelling catheter has been shown in multiple large clinical trials and smaller case studies to reduce the incidence of CAUTI, when compared with conventional catheters. Therefore, by prevention of CA-UTI, a significant reduction in morbidity and mortality, as well as the health care economic burden can be anticipated.

Silver has known antimicrobial properties and has not been tested in association with Foley's catheter, AgO impregnation over conventional Foley's catheter has a potential to reduce UTI. There are very few studies done in our country on testing the properties of

silver as an antimicrobial agent, thus there is need for study in this area.

Our goal in undertaking this study was to assess and compare the efficacy of silver impregnation over commercially available latex urinary catheters in prevention/ reduction of catheter related infections.

2. AIM AND OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

To compare and evaluate the efficacy of silver coated Foley's urinary catheter with conventional latex urinary catheter in prevention/reduction of catheter associated urinary tract infection.

3. RESEARCH HYPOTHESIS:

Silver coated Foley's urinary catheters reduce the risk of catheter associated urinary tract infection when compared with conventional Foley's catheter.

4. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

a) HISTORICAL ASPECT:

Since the primitive Egyptian civilization, there have been records of drainage of urinary retention. Other civilizations have also shown similar records like Asian, Chinese, Roman, Byzantine and Greek thus signifying the seriousness of this age-old issue. Various substances like straws, Reeds, Polished or Waxed rolled up leaves and hollow twigs have been used to drain the bladder¹⁴.

Use of urinary catheter for draining urine was the principle procedure performed by any physician in ancient times and this was emphasized in Hippocratic writings, “On Diseases” (around 400 BC)^{14,15}. It is surprising to note that the property of silver being an anti- microbial agent was suggested during medieval times, when a lean silver catheter was developed by Paulus Aegineta for draining bladder which later gained a lot of popularity¹⁴, Until the initiation of use of natural rubber as catheter use of silver was still favoured.

Eventually people such as Galen (2th century AD), Paulus (7th century AD), Avicenna (11th century AD) and others established the use of catheter for treatment of diseases such as Pyocystitis, Hematuria, Inflammation by introducing it into the bladder¹⁶.

The evolution of various equipment that we use in present day have been attributed to the crucial 19th century inventions. The Charriè`re unit to calculate catheter size came into existence and soon was accepted worldwide. This was initiated by Joseph F. B. (1 French unit equaling 0.33 mm)¹⁴.

Coudé tipped catheter (coudé means “elbow” in French) was introduced in 1836 by Mercier¹⁴. The Nelaton catheter, that is, a vulcanized rubber catheter which is soft, tubular and made with a solid straight tip with a hole at the side was developed by Auguste Nelaton in 1860¹⁴. Frederick E B Foley in 1930 came up with a novel idea of an expandable balloon attached to catheter tip as an anchor¹⁷. This became a fundamental concept for the rationale

of most of the lower urinary tract catheters used in current clinical practice¹⁷.

b) ANATOMICAL CONSIDERATIONS

MALE URETHRA

Average length of male urethra varies from 17.5 – 20 cms, as suggested from postmortem studies¹⁸. These values have been proven to be precise in recent studies by measuring urethra in vivo with a bladder catheter¹⁹.

Parts of the male urethra include, bladder neck or pre-prostatic urethra, prostatic urethra, membranous urethra and penile or spongy urethra. spongy urethra is sub divided into bulbous urethra, pendulous urethra and fossa navicularis. Another way of categorizing the male urethra are posterior segment comprising the prostatic and membranous urethra and anterior including the penile urethra. The diameter is variable in its entire length. A 24 F catheter can be passed through a normal healthy external meatus. Larger diameter is noticed in its proximal parts specially the prostatic which is the largest with 32 F diameter. Bladder neck admits 28 F device²⁰. The male urethra crosses the prostate followed by its course through deep perineal pouch, perineal membrane after which it enters the erectile tissues of penis finally ending at external urethral meatus (Fig. 1).

The two angles of penile urethra include;

- 1) Following its course through perineal membrane, the urethra curves anteriorly at the root of the penis, forming the **fixed angle**.
- 2) Another angle occurs distally where the unattached part of the penis curves inferiorly- when the penis is erect, this second angle disappears.

Figure- 1. Course of Male Urethra

Source- Gray's Anatomy for Students – 3rd ed. 2015; page no.424

FEMALE URETHRA

Urethra and bladder neck are usually present in the connective tissue of anterior vaginal wall in nulliparous women. Female urethra is about 4 cms, has three parts: Distal segment, Mid urethra, and the proximal segment²¹. There is an inferior angulation horizontally about mid-way in supine position the mean diameter being 22 F²². The female urethra is short, opens from bladder directly into perineum after crossing pelvic floor (Fig.2).

Figure- 2 Course of Female Urethra

Source- Gray's Anatomy for Students – 3rd ed. 2015; page no.424

c) INDICATIONS FOR URINARY CATHETERIZATION

THERAPEUTIC INDICATIONS

- Acute/ chronic urinary retention.
- Monitoring urinary output.
- Gross hematuria, to drain blood and clots
- Primary treatment in the management of urethral strictures²⁴.
- Intravesical instillation of drugs
 - For interstitial cystitis- dimethyl sulfoxide²³,
 - For intractable hematuria- Alum²³,
 - Invasive bladder cancer – Mitomycin C or Bacilli Calmette-Guérin (BCG) solution²³.
- Urogenital trauma

DIAGNOSTIC INDICATIONS

- Retrograde cystography, to inject contrast agent.
- To obtain an uncontaminated urine sample.
- Urodynamic studies to measure the intravesical and urethral pressure.
- Thermometer-tipped catheters – In lengthy surgeries providing both continuous thermometry and adequate drainage for urinary output measurement.

d) CATHETER SELECTION

A vast range of catheters are accessible for urinary catheterization. Variations in substance for manufacturing, length, diameter, appearance of catheter tip, number of channels, different coatings add to a wide range of choices.

Indications for use, amount of fluid required to drain, duration of catheter use, age, gender, previous history, anatomy decide the option of catheter design. Smallest size available should be chosen based on the following parameters (Table 1).

Table 1.

Catheter Size Based on Age

AGE IN YEARS	CATHETER SIZE (Fr)
<5	5-8
5-10	8-10
10-14	10
>14	10-14

Source: Campbell- Walsh UROLOGY. 11th ed. 2016, page no 120

The first trial of catheterization in an adult with no previous urinary complaints or known allergies should be attempted with a 16 F latex catheter.

Feeding tube insertion should be avoided due to their length and stiffness which may give rise to complications such as ischemic ulcers, urethral stricture, knotting of tube²⁵.

e) CATHETER DESIGN

Indwelling urinary catheter is a semi rigid, flexible tube which is used to drain the bladder but in turn block the urethra. there are mainly two types of urinary catheters available in current practice.

a. Single lumen catheter

It has only one lumen running its whole length open at both ends to facilitate urine drainage for single use and cannot be used for continuous urinary drainage. The advantage is that the intraluminal diameter of the catheter is large but cannot be used to keep the catheter in bladder for urinary drainage.

b. Double lumen/ Two-way catheter

It is the mostly widely used variety in clinical practice, it has two lumens running down its whole length. One of the lumen opens at both ends and allows for urine drainage. The other lumen has got a valve on the outside end and is connected to a balloon at the tip. The balloon is inflated with sterile water once it lies inside the bladder and thus predisposes for retention in bladder. Advantage in this type of catheter is that the intraluminal diameter of draining channel is larger as only two channels are accommodated. The disadvantage is that there is no channel for irrigation and other procedures²⁶ (Fig 4.).

c. Three -way catheter

The distal end of the catheter is provided with three ports/ lumens, one is a funnel

shaped channel for draining urine, other one is for inflation of balloon with sterile water for anchorage. The last one is for facilitating continuous bladder irrigation or for instillation of medication. This type is primarily needed following urologic surgery or in a case of bleeding from the bladder or prostate malignancy, where the bladder may need continuous or intermittent irrigation to clear blood clots or debris²⁷ (Fig 4.)

Figure. 3- Three-way, Two- way and Single lumen catheter

Source: Campbell- Walsh UROLOGY. 11th ed. 2016, page no 121

However, the addition of channels to single catheter design has several disadvantages. The extra channel reduces the internal diameter of catheter. Hence the internal diameter of a 24 F single channel catheter is more than that of a two-way 24 F which is again more than that of a 24 F three-way catheter.

There are two tip shapes of catheters- Nelaton blind ending straight tip and the Coude` tip/ elbowed/ Tiemann tip. Variations such as tapered tips or multiple side holes are present in a vast range of available catheters.

f) MATERIALS AND COATINGS

For day to day use catheters made of latex, rubber, silicon, Poly Vinyl Chloride (PVC) are preferred. For short term duration latex or rubber catheters are used because of their less cost and accessibility²³. For long duration silicon is favoured over latex due to less tissue inflammation.

As compared to others silicon is stiffer and has less risk of buckling in the presence of resistance²⁸. Various attempts for coating have been done to reduce trauma, urethritis and catheter associated urinary tract infection (CAUTI). Hydrophilic coated catheters can be used for intermittent catheterization. Advantages include more compliance, less trauma, reduced chance of UTI²³.

A current study by Bermingham showed that there was not much difference in risk of UTIs on comparing different catheter types used for Clean Intermittent Catheterization (CIC). In another study by Li and colleagues, with focus on spinal cord trauma patients documented that hydrophilic catheter usage in CIC significantly reduced UTI and Hematuria rates²³. Since uncoated catheters were most cost effective for CIC and the use of gel reservoir was 2nd most cost effective in Bermingham study, the routine use of hydrophilic catheters for CIC in non-spinal cord injury patients is not recommended^{23, 28}.

For short term use antibiotic coating may delay UTI chance (< 1 week). However, it is not much beneficial in long term use²⁴. Also, in some trials use of bacterial coated catheters with a non-virulent strain of E. Coli have shown good results. Although its effectiveness is still doubtful^{23, 25}.

In 2008, a meta-analysis published in Cochrane documented that use of silver coated catheters remarkably reduced the occurrence of UTI in both short- and long-term usage (>1

week)²⁴. In another recent RCT involving 6 thousand patients, antimicrobial impregnated catheters showed a notable benefit in minimizing CAUTI incidence as compared to polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE) catheters, on the other hand, silver catheters showed no significant change. Since remarkable benefit couldn't be appreciated in short term use with either groups, the routine use cannot be suggested²⁸.

Newer methods to impregnate catheter to amplify the biocompatibility are still being tried so as to prevent UTI and encrustation²⁹.

g) TECHNIQUE OF URETHRAL CATHETERIZATION

After gathering information regarding requirement of catheterization and taking a thorough history, previous urologic history, allergies catheterization should be attempted. This is required to decide upon correct catheter choice and for evaluation of risks and complications.

During catheterization, the doctor should stand at the side of patient which corresponds to the doctor's dominant hand. Materials required for the procedure should be kept ready on the sterile tray. Patient is placed in supine position and in case of female patients, lithotomy position is preferred. Under sterile precautions cleaning and draping are done. Before catheterizing, the balloon is checked for proper functioning. According to current American Heart Association protocols, there is no requirement of prophylactic treatment for infective endocarditis even in high risk patients for any urological procedure³⁰.

Before insertion, catheter should be lubricated properly for reducing chance of urethral trauma. Four types of lubricants are there; plain, lubricant anesthetic, lubricant disinfectant, lubricant anesthetic disinfectant.

Two percent lidocaine gel prior to catheterization has been considered safe and

effective since mid-20th century and has been in practice till now³¹. The absorption of 2 % lidocaine attains a very low peak concentration which is never toxic (i.e. up to 550 mg, which is 27 ml of 2% lidocaine)³². Although in patients with distorted mucosal barrier, absorption is found to be more which causes high peak serum concentration in minutes causing toxicity. Side effects documented are confusion, lethargy, seizures, disorientation, anaphylactic shock³³.

According to Chitale and Mc Farlane, pain scale was similar for plain versus anesthetic lubricant for flexible cystoscopy³⁴. However, Ho and colleagues stated that anesthetic lubricant usage is paradoxically more painful than plain lubricant²³. On the other hand, if we decrease the temperature of lubricant up to 4 degree centigrade, it notably reduces pain in comparison with lubricant at room or body temperature most probably due to cryo-analgesic effect³⁵.

Application of the anesthetic lubricant for more than 10-15 mins is needed for its action to start³⁶. Also, it has been seen that little delay (< 15 mins) will not cause any benefit in comparison to no delay²³. In females, the action of anesthetic lubricant starts few minutes after its insertion²³. Various studies show contradictory conclusions with respect of usage of anesthetic versus plane lubricant. This was supported by Patel and colleagues. Whereas Aaronson and colleagues documented a favorable effect with respect to anesthetic lubricants.^{23, 36}

Hence depending on this information regular use of anesthetic lubricant is questionable, but when indicated it has to be applied slowly (3-10 secs) and about 20 ml cooled lubricant should be used and allowed to act for about 15 mins²³.

After retracting the prepuce, the external meatus is visualized. If there is phimosis, catheter can be inserted blindly with smaller flexible catheter. In patients with hypospadias where

there is blind ending navicular fossa catheter should be avoided. If there is a stricture or a stenosis, a smaller size catheter should be tried initially. If catheterization is unsuccessful, careful dilatation is tried.

Under aseptic precautions, skin and meatus are cleaned and draped. First the penis is to be held with the non-dominant hand. This hand is now considered unsterile. The penis is straightened by pulling the shaft upward. Following lubrication catheter is introduced into the meatus and pushed to about 7-12 cms. Penis is made parallel to the patient by making it horizontal. There may be minimal resistance at the membranous urethra. Catheter is inserted up to the Y junction. There should be spontaneous drainage of urine if bladder is full. If not, slight suprapubic massage is done or by flushing with sterile fluid followed by aspiration should drain urine. If after all efforts there is no urine in catheter, either bladder is empty or catheter is not in position. Pus / blood/ lubricant jelly may block the catheter.

Once the catheter is in the bladder, balloon is filled with sterile water. Sterile water has been considered ideal for inflation of balloon if catheter requirement is for many days³⁷. Saline or glucose fluids if used for inflation can cause precipitation, however not proven evidently²³. After catheterization, prepuce is retracted back to prevent paraphimosis. In order to avoid pressure ulceration at the pendulous curve of urethra and iatrogenic hypospadias, the catheter must be fixed at an upright position. Iatrogenic hypospadias leading to deformities can happen if it remains unattended.^{23, 37}

Catheter should be connected to sterile urine collecting bag so as to ensure a closed drainage circuit, to be kept in dependent position for urine to be drained. It is important to note that even though it is a belief that there might be problems like hematuria, hypotension, pain, due to sudden emptying of bladder, but drainage has been proved to be efficacious and safe³⁸.

h) COMPLICATIONS

Urinary catheterization is a routine procedure in hospital. Although it is very important it can have various complications.

It has been seen that at any point during their stay, 15-25% of patients require catheterization²³. UTI is commonly seen, about 35 % of Nosocomial infections. About 95% of UTI is seen in ICU set up from catheters³⁹. Urinary catheterization has been documented up to 15-40 % of cases and is associated with longer hospital stay. The cost of CAUTI accounts to about \$ 300 million in United States. Various projects have been undertaken to improve the quality which have led to the reduction in CAUTI incidence.^{23, 39}

In 2009, CAUTI definition has been changed according to which asymptomatic bacteriuria is excluded⁴⁰. In recent guidelines, “CAUTI is defined as significant bacteriuria in a patient with symptoms/ signs indicating a UTI, whereas asymptomatic bacteriuria refers to significant bacteriuria in asymptomatic patients.” Antibiotics are not required for asymptomatic bacteriuria. Since sufficient proof is not there regarding benefit following treatment of asymptomatic bacteriuria to reduce morbidity and mortality, the European Association of Urology (EAU) and Infectious Disease Society of America (IDSA) does not recommend any antibiotic therapy for the same²³. Indwelling catheter for long duration of 6 days or more, is a significant risk factor for CAUTI. Catheterization outside the operation theatre, female, body mass index (BMI) more than 30, diabetes and any evidence of foci of infection are to their risk factors for CAUTI⁴¹.

Some of the recommended protocols to prevent CAUTI are to ensure to a closed drainage system, avoid catheter use as much as possible, to remove catheter early and to avoid irrigation routinely. Catheterization should be done under aseptic precautions and using sufficient lubrication. According to a recent study there was not much difference in

incidence of UTI for prolonged duration when compared with respect to various types of catheter^{23, 42}. There is lack of proof to suggest the use of a particular catheter type. Short course of antibiotics for 5 days along with change of catheter versus long course (10 days) without change are equally effective⁴².

In patients with CIC (Clean Intermittent Catheterization) use of long course of antibiotics as prophylaxis has not been seen to reduce the incidence of UTI notably. However, in patients with spina bifida, disruption of long course antibiotic prophylaxis leads to insignificant rise in UTI without clinical significance. After short term use and removal of catheter, prophylactic antibiotic course even for short term duration has been encouraged as well as disapproved²³. According to American Urological Association (AUA) recommendations in 2008, use of prophylactic antibiotics following removal of catheter has been suggested if there is presence of bacteriuria especially in patients like older age, immunosuppression, corticosteroid use⁴³. The IDSA has disapproved the use of antibiotic course as prophylaxis before catheter is removed or changed in 2010²³. A recent study documented reduced incidence of UTI on administration of prophylactic antibiotics after removal of catheter post-surgery²³. If about 25 % of in- patients are considered to be catheterized at any point in the course of their stay, suggesting antibiotics routinely after removal of catheter would lead to increased risk of antibiotic resistance and drug related adverse effects. Therefore, considering antibiotic prophylaxis only in patients with risk factors is advisable as recommended by AUA panel.

A recent study showed that complications other than CAUTI are more frequently seen in long term catheterized patients i.e. four-fold times. They include peri catheter urine leakage, accidental removal, catheter block, hematuria, bladder calculus, bladder cancer. Patients with spine injuries are at increased risk for these complications⁴⁴.

One of the important complications is difficulty in removing catheter. Following urethroplasty or radical prostatectomy catheter entrapment with in anastomotic sutures is one of the serious post-operative complications. If sutures are absorbable catheter can be removed one to two weeks following procedure. If they are non- absorbable, they can be divided by laser with the help of semi rigid ureteroscope^{23, 44}. There is a possibility of catheter being bound to bladder neck due to balloon cuffing following deflation which usually depends on the material of the catheter, duration of usage, method of deflation, UTI. Among these duration of usage is the most important factor. This can be avoided by using hydrogel coated or PTFE catheters or deflating the balloon slowly⁴⁵. A method was suggested by Gonzalgo in which of 0.5 – 1 ml of fluid can be infused in the balloon due to which the cuff gets smoothed as a result of which catheter can be easily removed⁴⁶.

There can be instances where it is difficult to deflate the balloon. It can be resolved by infusion of an extra 1-2 ml fluid in balloon and retry to aspirate. Letting the balloon burst by over inflating it might be painful to the patient and could lead to retained catheter bits in the bladder and hence to be avoided. Another alternative is to cut off the inflation valve if not working properly. In case of failure guided wire can be passed through the inflation channel and balloon can be perforated. If all attempts fail, ultrasound guided needle puncture of balloon is the ultimate choice. The balloon deflation is difficult due to encrustation which can be because of prolonged catheterization. There are reports suggesting that one of the main reasons for encrustation is infection due to *Proteus mirabilis*. As a result of this there can be repeated catheter block⁴⁷. Gentle traction to the catheter may help to remove encrustation and hence aid removal of catheter. Even after this if it is not solved, ultrasound or X- Ray can be done for confirmation of encrustation. Semi rigid ureteroscope guided Holmium: YAG Laser can be used to dislodge the encrustation. Asking the patient to increase fluid intake and intake of citrate may prevent this issue in

known calculus and chronic catheterized patients^{23, 47}.

Another common problem is stricture urethra. About 11.2 % of strictures which need urethroplasty are due to catheterization in patients as reported by Lumen and coworkers. It causes multifocal or pan urethral strictures²³.

According to Fenton and colleagues about 32 % of strictures were caused by iatrogenic trauma, among which 36.5 % were due to longer duration of catheterization. The suggested reason being inflammation and ischemia of urethra finally leading to stricture²³. Also, if the balloon is inflated in the prostatic urethra, it can cause severe hematuria, urethral rupture and finally stricture⁴⁸.

i) PREVENTION OF IATROGENIC TRAUMA

When catheter balloon is kept in wrong position the pressure exerted is much higher. As compared to 10 ml, 5 ml causes much less force of extraction in balloon⁴⁹. While inflation if resistance is encountered, we should suspect that catheter is in wrong position. If patients are at risk of trauma, balloon has to be inflated with 5 ml to reduce the trauma risk.

For longer duration of catheterization 16 F size catheter is preferred. When longer duration of catheterization is required, a low threshold suprapubic catheter can be used²³. There can be a reduction in trauma due to catheterization by 5-fold with proper training, knowledge and skill⁵⁰.

A study conducted by A. Maya Nandkumar, titled ‘**Antimicrobial Silver Oxide Incorporated Urinary Catheters for Infection Resistance**’ in 2010⁴ has described a method of incorporating Silver oxide into finished Latex Foley’s catheters without substantially altering its properties. The method is easy to perform, does not need special equipment and can be

easily incorporated into the manufacturing process. It has effective antimicrobial activity which prevents both bacterial adhesion and subsequent biofilm formation and is non-cytotoxic, thus fulfilling its promise of an effective anti-microbial surface.

In a study conducted by Patrick HY Chung et al, titled '**A prospective interventional study to examine the effect of a silver alloy and hydrogel-coated catheter on the incidence of catheter-associated urinary tract infection**' 2017⁵¹ found that the incidences of catheter-associated urinary tract infection per 1000 catheter-days were 6.4 and 9.4, in silver coated and uncoated catheters respectively (P=0.095). There was a 31% reduction in the incidence of catheter-associated urinary tract infection per 1000 catheter-days in the silver-coated group. Silver alloy and hydrogel-coated catheters appear to be effective in preventing catheter-associated urinary tract infection based on the latest surveillance definition. The effect is perhaps more prominent in long-term users and female patients.

A study conducted by James W. Lederer, William R. Jarvis, Lendon Thomas, Jaime Ritter, titled '**Multicenter Cohort Study to Assess the Impact of a Silver-Alloy and Hydrogel-Coated Urinary Catheter on Symptomatic Catheter-Associated Urinary Tract Infections**' 2014⁵² found 47% relative reduction in the CAUTI rate was observed with the silver-alloy hydrogel catheter compared to the standard catheter (0.945/1000 patient days Vs 0.498/1000 patient days) (odds ratio = 0.53; P < .0001; 95% CI: 0.45-0.62) thus use of a silver-alloy hydrogel urinary catheter reduced symptomatic Catheter Associated UTI occurrences.

A study conducted by David Roe¹, Balu Karandikar¹, Nathan Bonn-Savage¹, Bruce Gibbins¹ and Jean-Baptiste Rouillet² titled '**Antimicrobial surface functionalization of plastic catheters by silver nanoparticles**' 2008⁵³ found that sustained release of silver was demonstrated over a period of 10 days. Coated catheters showed significant in vitro

antimicrobial activity and prevented biofilm formation using *Escherichia coli*, *Enterococcus*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, coagulase-negative staphylococci, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and *Candida albicans*. Because of the demonstrated antimicrobial properties of silver, it may be useful in reducing the risk of infectious complications in patients with indwelling catheters.

A study conducted by Tobi B. Karchmer, Eve T. Giannetta, Carlene A. Muto, Barbara A. Strain, Barry M Farr, titled '**Randomised cross over study of silver coated urinary catheters in Hospitalised patients' in 2000**¹³ found that the relative risk of infection per 100 silver coated catheters used on study ward with uncoated catheters was 0.68(95% CI, P= .001). The incidence of catheter associated urinary tract infection was found to be 2.13 per 100 silver coated catheters Vs 3.12 per 100 uncoated catheters.

5.MATERIALS AND METHODS:

SOURCE OF DATA:

All patients coming to B.L.D.E (D.U)'s Sri B M Patil Medical College, Hospital and Research Centre, admitted and had an indication for Urinary Bladder Catheterization.

Period of the study was from November 2017 to May 2019.

METHOD OF COLLECTION OF DATA

The Patients admitted in B.LD.E. (DU)'s Shri. B. M. Patil Medical College, Hospital and Research Centre, Vijayapur in Surgery Department during period November 2017 to May 2019 with a sample size of 120 in each group comprising of a total 240 patients were allotted to either of the group to ensure that the two groups are adequately matched with respect to age, sex ratio and patients on systemic antibiotics. The patients were explained in detail about both the procedure and complications. Data collection included indication for catheterization, type of catheter used and duration of catheterization, urine for pus cells, organisms isolated, and demographic information. Bacteriuria as evaluated by urine culture and urine pus cells were the outcome variables used to indicate urinary tract infection (Catheter associated), which is defined by centers for disease control and Prevention (CDC) as "In patients with indwelling catheter in place for 48 h or more with presence of at least 10^3 colony forming units (cfu)/ml of 1-2 micro-organism by urine culture³.

INCLUSION CRITERIA

Adult patients aged between 18 and 89 years admitted for surgical conditions which needed intervention or prolonged stay with requirement of monitoring of urinary output or catheterization for various reasons who will need catheterization for 3 or more days, such as,

- ✓ Patients with negative urine culture
- ✓ Patients who had an indwelling urinary catheter for 3 or more calendar days after hospital admission were included in the study.

EXCLUSION CRITERIA

- ✓ Patients with urinary diversions.
- ✓ Certain pre-existing conditions affecting the bladder (E.g. active bladder cancer, chronic indwelling urinary catheter in place.
- ✓ Those undergoing an invasive urologic surgery.
- ✓ Patients with pre-existing UTI.
- ✓ Patients with sterile Bacteriuria.

METHOD OF PREPARING CATHETER:

The methodology described here is a patented technology, where in commercially available Foley's urinary catheter made up of latex material were used in silver impregnation⁴. It is a simple to perform procedure and the necessary substrates and materials required are,

1. FOLEY'S CATHETER

It is a flexible rubber tube catheter used for drainage of urine. It was named after Dr. Frederic Eugene Basil Foley, an American Urologist who first came up with the original design in 1929. It is made up of either latex material, silicon or can be made from Teflon. It has two lumens, one for inflating the balloon and the other for drainage, running down its whole length with a retention balloon near the tip. Foley's catheter is available with short and long nosed tips. The size of the retention balloon ranges between 5-50 ml and the diameter (luminal) ranges from 12 to 30 F. It is found that the

balloon can be overinflated (at least up to twice their stated capacity) without breakage⁵⁴. The silver oxide impregnated Foley's catheter was sterilized using an Ethylene Oxide sterilisation for 48 hrs.

Figure 4- Classical two- way Foley's catheter.

Source: Handbook of Urology: Diagnosis and Therapy. 3rd ed. 2004; p-65

2. TOLUENE (METHYLEBENZENE)

It is an aromatic hydrocarbon, which is colourless liquid, water insoluble, chemically it is CH₃ group attached to a phenyl group. It is predominantly used as an industrial feedstock and a solvent. In our study it was used as a solvent⁵⁵.

3. SILVER NITRATE

Silver as silver nitrate is a chemical element with symbol Ag, derived from the Latin word argentum; meaning "shiny" or "white" with atomic number 47. Silver and its compounds have an oligodynamic effect and toxic for bacteria, algae, fungi. Its antibacterial function is dependent on Ag⁺ ions. Effectiveness of silver compounds as an antiseptic is based on the ability of biologically active silver ions to irreversibly damage key enzyme systems in the cell membranes of pathogens. It was observed that, on applying an electric current across silver electrodes enhances antibiotic action at the anode, likely due to the release of silver ions into the bacterial culture⁵⁶.

Silver and its applications in current clinical practice

- ❖ Silver is in use since 1960, Silver Sulphadiazine (SSD) is used as a topical antibiotic agent in wounds/ burns to prevent infection⁵⁷.
- ❖ Its application in specific wound management was strongly supported by a 2018 Cochrane's review, which concluded that silver compounds containing dressings may have increased the probability of healing for venous ulcers⁵⁸.

Another meta-analysis in 2017 over 15 years (2000-2015) concluded that “the evidence base for silver in wound management is significantly better than perceived in the current scientific debate” and if applied selectively for short periods of time, silver has antimicrobial effects, produces an improvement in quality of life and shows good cost effectiveness⁵⁹.

- ❖ A 2015 system systematic review suggested silver coated endotracheal tubes reduced the risk of contracting Ventilator Associated Pneumonia (VAP)⁶⁰.
- ❖ Its role in application to urinary catheters is supported by a 2014 cohort study, which observed that using a silver alloy hydrogel urinary catheter did reduce symptomatic CAUTI occurrences⁵².

4. DIMETHYL ACETAMIDE/ FORMAMIDE

Formamide (also known as methanamide) is an amide derived from Formica acid. It is a clear liquid with a pungent (ammonia) like odour, which is used as a solvent for preparing silver nitrate solution⁶¹.

PROCEDURE

Foley's catheter commercially available is dipped in an organic solvent such as Toluene for about 30 secs. Silver Nitrate is then mixed in Formamide liquid to prepare a solution of silver nitrate. For every catheter prepared, 1 gram of silver nitrate was used. Following which the

catheter is then placed in the solution prepared. The solution is then heated in a temperature-controlled water bath at about 70- 80 degree for 15 mins.

Figure 5 - Temperature Controlled Water Bath

Source – *BLDE (DU) Central Research Laboratory, Vijayapur*

This will lead to silver oxide impregnation over the intra-luminal and extra-luminal surfaces of catheter. Further the Catheter is washed with distilled water to remove excess of formamide. Catheter is then air dried and is further subjected to Ethylene Oxide sterilization for 48 hours.

Figure 6- Ethylene Oxide Sterilizer

Source- *Shri B. M Patil Medical College, Hospital, Vijayapur, Karnataka*

Figure 7- Conventional Foley 'S' Catheter

Source- *Shri B. M Patil Medical College, Hospital, Vijayapur, Karnataka.*

Figure 8- Silver Oxide Impregnated Foley's Catheter

Source- *BLDE (DU) Central Research Laboratory, Vijayapur.*

SAMPLING

A study conducted by **Sanjay Saint et al**⁶. titled ‘The Efficacy of Silver Alloy-coated Urinary Catheters in Preventing Urinary Tract Infection: A Meta-Analysis’ published in 1998 is taken as reference study.

With the incidence of UTI by silver coated catheter- 11% and that of conventional Foley’s catheter- 24%, at 99% confidence level and with 80% power in the study, total sample size of 240 was taken. Thus, study group had 120 and control group had 120 patients (240/2).

Formula for estimating sample size: $n = \frac{(z\alpha + z\beta)^2 * P * Q}{d^2}$

d²

Where,

n= estimated sample size

d= difference between two proportions

Z α = confidence level (99%)

Z β =Power (80%)

P = incidence of infection

Q= 100-P

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS-

The data obtained were recorded in a Microsoft Excel sheet, and statistical analysis was performed using statistical package for the social sciences (Version 17). Results are presented as drawings, Mean \pm SD, counts and percentages.

Categorical variables were compared using chi square test, quantitative variables were compared using Mann Whitney U test. For all tests, significance was achieved at p<0.05. All statistical tests performed were two tailed.

6.RESULTS:

Table 2. Distribution of patients according to Age in study and control group.

Age (Years)	Study group		Control group	
	No. of patients	Percentage	No. of patients	Percentage
< 20	2	1.7	0	0
20 - 29	13	10.8	11	9.2
30 - 39	24	20.0	27	22.5
40 - 49	27	22.5	40	33.3
50 - 59	23	19.2	20	16.7
60 - 69	22	18.3	13	10.8
70+	9	7.5	9	7.5
Total	120	100.0	120	100.0

Figure 9- Distribution of patients according to Age in study and control group.

The above table shows the distribution of age between the two groups **Study** (silver oxide coated catheter) and **Control** (conventional latex catheter). There were only two patients in the study group with less than 20 yrs of age. 13 patients were between 20-29 years in study group and 11 in control, 24 patients were between 30-39 years in study group and 27 in control group ,27 patients were in between 40-49 years of age group in study and 40 in control group , 23 patients were between 50-59 years in study and 20 in control group, 22 patients were between 60-69 years of age in study group and 13 in control group, 9 patients were above 70 years in each study and control group.

Table 3. Distribution of patients according to Gender in study and control group.

Gender	Study group		Control group		Chi square test	P value
	No. of patients	Percentage	No. of patients	Percentage		
Female	54	45.0	45	37.5	X ² =1.393	P=0.2380
Male	66	55.0	75	62.5		NS
Total	120	100.0	120	100.0		
NS: Not significant						

Out of 120 patients, 66 were males and 54 were females in Study group.

Out of 120 patients, 75 were males and 45 were females in no drain group.

Figure- 10. Distribution of patients according to Gender in study and control group.

Table 4. Mean age between study and control group.

Age (Years)	Mean (Median)	±SD	Mann Whitney U test	P value
Study	47.63(48)	15.04	U=7103	P=00.8763 NS
Control	47.73(47)	13.07		
NS: Not significant				

The mean age was 47.63 ± 15.04 years in study group and 47.1 ± 13.07 years in control group.

Table 5. Comparison of **Body Mass Index (BMI)** between Study and Control groups

Comparison of	Study group		Control group		Mann Whitney U test	P- value
	Mean (Median)	±SD	Mean (Median)	±SD		
BMI	20.03(19.4)	1.83	20.18(19.4)	2.20	7189.5	P=0.9852 NS
NS: Not significant						

It was observed in our study that, the Mean & Median BMI in study group was found to be 20.3 and 19.4 respectively. In control group, the Mean & Median was found to be 20.18 and 19.4 respectively.

Table 6. Indications for catheterization in study and control group

SL NO	Indications	Study	Control	Total
1	Split Thickness Skin Grafting	22	14	36
2	Necrotising Fascitis	17	18	35
3	Fracture of Lower Limb	18	17	35
4	Exploratory Laparotomy	8	17	25
5	Deep Venous Thrombosis	13	15	25
6	Resection anastomosis of small bowel	11	7	18
7	Quadriplegia/ Hemiplegia	11	5	16

8	Blunt Trauma Abdomen	7	8	15
9	Sub- acute Intestinal Obstruction	4	7	11
10	Bedsore	2	7	9
11	Neurogenic Bladder	3	3	6
12	Sepsis	3	2	5
13	Chronic Kidney Disease	1	2	3
14	Thoracotomy	0	1	1

Out of the various causes for monitoring urine output urinary catheterization done, most common indication was in patients who were immobilised following Split thickness skin grafting surgery (36 patients), followed by Necrotising Fasciitis (35 patients), fracture of the lower limbs such as fracture of femur, tibia, hip joints, calcaneum and etc.

Other indications for catheterization were as followed, Exploratory Laparotomy (25 patients), Deep Venous Thrombosis (25 patients), Resection anastomosis of the small bowel for various reasons (18), patients immobilised due to pressure sores (16 patients), Blunt trauma abdomen (15 patients), Sub- acute Intestinal Obstruction (11 patients), neurogenic bladder (6 patients), Sepsis (5 patients), Chronic kidney disease (3 patients) and one patient was catheterized pre operatively in a case of Open thoracotomy.

Figure 11- Indications for Catheterization in study group

Figure 12- Indications for Catheterization in study group

Table 7. Comparison of urine for **pus cells** in patients between study and control group

Urine pus cells	Study group		Control group		Chi square test	P value
	No. of patients	Percentage	No. of patients	Percentage		
Day 1						
Present	7	5.08	9	7.5	X ² =0.0803	P=0.7768
Absent	113	94.2	111	92.5		NS
Day 3						
Present	26	21.7	29	24.2	X ² =0.2123	P=0.6450
Absent	94	78.3	91	75.9		NS
Day 7						
Present	47	39.2	64	53.3	X ² =40.844	P=0.0277
Absent	73	60.08	56	46.7		HS
Total	120	100.0	120	100.0		
NS: Not significant HS: Highly significant						

In the present study, urine for pus cells was taken as positive when the count was more than 10 pus cells per hpf⁶². It was observed that the number of patients with significant pus cells (pus cells > 10 /hpf) in urine on day 7 was significantly lower in study group **P value 0.0277**. There was no difference in p value between study and control group at the end of day 1 (after 48 hrs of catheter insertion) and on day 3, with p value of 0.77 and 0.64 respectively.

Figure 13- Comparison of urine for **pus cells** in patients between study and control group.

Table 8. Comparison of **Urine Culture** between **study** and control group

Urine Culture	Study group		Control group		Chi square test	P value
	No. of patients	Percentage	No. of patients	Percentage		
E. COLI	13	27.6	23	33.3	X ² =7.397	
S. AUREUS	11	23.4	13	18.8		
K. PNEUMONIA	6	12	15	21.7		
P. AUREUGINOSA	8	17	5	7.2		

C. FRUEIDI	3	6.3	4	5.7	P=0.4945 NS
C.NON-ALBICANS	3	6.3	3	6.3	
E. SAPROPHYTICUS	2	4.2	4	5.7	
PROTEUS	0	0	2	2.8	
C. ALBICANS	1	2.1	0	0	
NS: Not significant					

It was observed in that the most common organism isolated was found to be E. Coli with 27.6%, followed by S. Aureus with 23.4 %. Other organisms isolated with lesser frequency were P. Aeruginosa and K. Pneumoniae with 17 % and 12 % respectively. Other rare organisms isolated were C. Albicans, C. Non- Albicans and E. Saprophyticus.

In Control group, K. Pneumoniae (21.7 %) was the most common organism after E. coli (33.3 %), followed by S. Aureus being 18.8 %. Two patients were found to be positive with proteus species being 2.8 %.

Figure 14- Organisms isolated in Study group

Figure 15- Organisms isolated in control group.

However, Comparison for the difference in the incidence of type organisms isolated between study and control group revealed no statistical difference with P- value 0.49.

Table 9. Comparison of symptomatic CAUTI between study and control group.

SYMPTOMS (fever/ suprapubic pain, etc.)	Study group		Control group		Chi square test	P value
	No. of patients	Percentage	No. of patients	Percentage		
Yes	12	10.0	16	13.3	X ² =0.6469	P=0.4212
No	108	90.0	104	86.7		
Total	120	100.0	120	100.0		
NS: Not significant						

It was observed that out of 49 patients positive for urine culture, only 12 patients had symptoms like fever, suprapubic pain/ tenderness. Whereas 16 patients were symptomatic out of 69 patients positive for urine culture. However, there was no statistical difference between the study and control groups with P- value 0.42.

Figure- 16. Comparison symptomatic CAUTI between study and control group.

7.DISCUSSION

In this study a total of 240 patients were included, of which 120 patients with Silver Oxide impregnated Foley's catheter were placed in study group and 120 patients with Conventional Foley's catheter were in control group.

AGE GROUP & GENDER

In our study, 22.5 % of patients in the study group were in the age group between 40- 49 years, followed by 20 % of patients in the age group 30-39 years, followed by 19.2 % in 50-59 years and 18.3 % in the age group 60-69 years. It was observed that 10.8 % of the patients were in the age group 20-29 years, 7.5 % of them were above 70 years of age and 1.7 % in the age group less than 20 years.

On the other hand, 33.3 % of patients in the control group belonged to the age group 40- 49 years, followed by 22.5 % of patients between age group 30-39 years. 16.7 % of the patients belonged to age group 50-59 years, 10.8 % patients in the age group 60-69 years, 9.2 % of them between 20-29 years and 7.5 % of the control group patients were more than 75 years of age.

In our study, 45 % of the patients in the study group were females and 55 % were males, where as 37.5 % of the patients in the control group were females and 63.5 % were males. It was observed that there was no statistical difference between the groups with respect to gender with P value 0.238. Overall, 41 % of the patients were females and 59 % of them were males.

Sangamithra. V et al³ in their study reported 65% of patients were males and 37 % were females.

MEAN AGE

The mean age was found to be 47.63 ± 15.04 in study group and 47.1 ± 13.07 in the control group. There was no statistical difference of age between the groups with P value of 0.087.

A study conducted by Patrick H. Y Chung et al reported a mean age of 81.1 %⁵¹.

COMPARISON OF BODY MASS INDEX (BMI)

On comparing the BMI between the study and control group, it was observed that, there was no statistical difference between the study and control group with P- value being 0.98.

INDICATIONS FOR CATHETERIZATION

On comparing the various indications for catheterization, it was seen that the two groups were statistically not significant.

COMPARISON OF URINE FOR PUS CELLS

In our study, it was seen that the urine examination for pus cells at the end of Day1 (48 hours after admission) was found positive (urine pus cells more than 10/ hpf was taken as cut off in our study⁶⁵) in 5.08 % in study group and 7.5 % in the control group. There was no statistical difference between the incidence of urine for pus cells between the study and control group with p value of 0.77. Similarly, there was no statistical difference between the two groups with incidence of 21.7% positive in study group and 29 % in the control group (p value- 0.64).

Whereas, urine for pus cells was found positive in 39.2 % in study group and 53.3 % positive in control group in a sample size of 120 in each group. There was difference in the incidence of patients with positive urine analysis with significantly less patients in study group with p value 0.027.

In a study conducted by Sangamithra V. et al observed that incidence of Urinary Tract Infection in a tertiary care set up was found 10 % during first three days of urinary tract catheterization, followed by 29 % between 4- 7 days and 52 % between 7-14 days³.

In a study conducted by Thibon, P. et al⁶⁵ observed that, the mean cumulative incidence of UTI related to catheterization was 11.1 %, 11.9 % in the group with classical catheter and 10 % in the group with hydrogel and silver salts coated catheter. The overall incidence density was 19 per thousand days of catheterization, 21 in the classical catheter and 18 per thousand days of catheterization in the other group. The differences between the two groups were not significant concluding that there is not enough number of studies to support the role of silver coated catheters in prevention of CAUTI.

URINE CULTURE

It was observed in our study that most common organism isolated was Escherichia Coli (27.6 % in study group, followed by Staphylococcus Aureus (23.4%), Pseudomonas Aeruginosa (17%), Klebsiella Pneumoniae (12 %), Candida Non-albicans (6.3 %), Citrobacter freundii (6.3 %) and Candida Albicans (2.1 %) respectively in decreasing frequency.

Whereas, most common organism isolated in control group was Escherichia Coli (33.3%), followed by Klebsiella Pneumoniae (21.7 %), Staphylococcus Aureus (18.8%), Pseudomonas Aeruginosa (7.2%), Citrobacter freundii (5.7 %), Enterococcus Saprophyticus (5.7%), Candida Non-albicans (4.3 %), and Proteus species in 2.8 % cases.

Overall the most common organisms isolated were Escherichia Coli, Staphylococcus Aureus, Klebsiella Pneumoniae, Pseudomonas Aeruginosa, Citrobacter freundii and Candida species in decreasing frequency.

In a study conducted by Sangamithra V et al³ found that the most common organism isolated was Escherichia Coli, followed by Enterococcus Saprophyticus, Klebsiella species and Pseudomonas species in decreasing order of frequency. Whereas, Proteus species and Acinetobacter were found in 3-4 % cases.

In a study conducted by Thibon, P. et al revealed that, from 22 cases of infection there were 23 microbial isolates found; one patient was found to be infected with more than one type of microorganism. There was no significant difference between the types of organisms isolated with the two types of catheter⁶³.

SYMPTOMATIC CAUTI

In our study, it was observed that 10 % of the patients were symptomatic although they were found to be significantly positive for urine pus cells/ urine culture on urine analysis. They had presented with symptoms of fever/ chills, suprapubic pain, or change in urine character. Whereas, 13 % of the patients among 120 patients had symptomatic CAUTI. There was no reported case of complicated UTI or reaction to the silver oxide impregnated Foley's catheter in our study.

In a study conducted by Tambyah PA et al titled "Catheter-associated urinary tract infection is rarely symptomatic: a prospective study of 1,497 catheterized patients" found that, out of 235 new cases of nosocomial CAUTI during the study period, More than 90% of the infected patients were asymptomatic; In the subset analysis, there were no significant differences among patients with and without CAUTI in signs or symptoms commonly associated with urinary tract infection—fever, dysuria, urgency, or flank pain—or in leucocytosis⁶⁴.

8. CONCLUSION:

In our study, there was no statistical difference in distribution of patients between the study group and control group with respect to Age and Gender.

Urine examination for evidence of pus cells was found significantly low in the study group on the Day 7 or more (up to 14 days) of urinary tract catheterization with P value – **0.027**, whereas there was no difference on the incidence at the end of Day1 or Day3. Thus, we can infer from the above results that the Silver Oxide impregnated Foley's catheter was efficacious in reducing the occurrence of Catheter related urinary tract infections.

It was observed from our study that the Silver Oxide impregnation to plain Foleys catheter has the potential to prevent/reduce the incidence of catheter associated urinary tract infections in patients who need longer duration of catheterization for various reasons. It was also observed in our study that duration of study was a significant risk factor in predisposing a patient to infections.

9.SUMMARY:

Catheter Associated Urinary Tract Infection is the most prevalent form of Hospital Acquired Infections (HAI), causing significant morbidity and mortality. It leads to prolonged hospitalization and increased cost of treatment.

Our goal in undertaking this study was to assess and compare the efficacy of silver impregnation over commercially available latex urinary catheters in prevention/ reduction of catheter related infections.

Period of the study was from November 2017 to May 2019, with a total sample size of 240.

Urine for pus cells was used as the end variable for diagnosing CAUTI and on comparing the values at the end of day 1 (48 hours after admission), on Day3, and Day seven or more, we observed that there was significant difference in the incidence of CAUTI between the study and the control group on the Day 7 or more.

There was no difference between the groups compared with respect to Age and Sex. The most common organism isolated in our study was Escherichia. Coli, followed by Staphylococcus Aureus, Klebsiella Pneumonia, Pseudomonas species, and others.

The incidence of symptomatic CAUTI was found to be between 10-13 % in our study.

Thus, we can conclude that the current research hypothesis of silver coated urinary catheters reducing risk of CAUTI holds good with a positive result on the incidence of CAUTI on Day 7 group with significant P- value of 0.0277, but there is a greater need for further studies on this topic as CAUTI is a potentially preventable condition.

10.BIBILOGRAPHY:

1. Alberto F. Monegro, Hariharan Regunath. Hospital Acquired Infections. [Updated 2018 Oct 27]. In: StatPearls [Internet]. Treasure Island (FL): StatPearls Publishing; 2019 Jan-
2. Alberto F. Monegro, Hariharan Regunath. Hospital Acquired Infections [Internet]. StatPearls [Internet]. U.S. National Library of Medicine; 2018 Sep
3. Sangamithra V, Sneka, Praveen Shabana and Manonmoney. Incidence of Catheter Associated Urinary Tract Infection in Medical ICU in a Tertiary Care Hospital. *Int.J.Curr.Microbiol.App.Sci.* 2017; 6:662-669
4. Nandkumar AM, Ranjit MC, Pradeep Kumar SS, Hari PR, Ramesh P, Sreenivasan K. Antimicrobial Silver Oxide Incorporated Urinary Catheters for Infection Resistance. *Trends Biomater. Artif. Organs.* 2010; 24:156-164
5. Jeong I, Park S, Jeong J S, Kim DS, Choi YS, Lee YS, et al. Comparison of catheter-associated urinary tract infection rates by perineal care agents in intensive care units. *Asian Nurs. Res.* 2010; 4:142-150
6. Saint S, Elmore JG, Sullivan SD, Emerson SS, Koepsell TD. The Efficacy of Silver Alloy-coated Urinary Catheters in Preventing Urinary Tract Infection: A Meta-Analysis. *Am J Med.* 1998; 105:236 –241
7. Platt R, Polk BF, Murdock B, Rosner B. Mortality associated with nosocomial urinary tract infection. *N Engl J Med.* 1982; 307:637–642
8. Carr HA. A short history of the Foley catheter: from handmade instrument to infection-prevention device. *J Endourol.* 2000; 14: 5-8

9. Ellis H. Therapeutic milestones. The Foley catheter. *Br J Clin Pract.* 1988; 42:248-249
10. Lapidus J, Diokno AC, Silber SJ, Lowe BS. Clean, intermittent self-catheterization in the treatment of urinary tract disease. *J Urology.* 1972; 107: 458-461
11. Marino RA, Mooppan UM, et al. History of urethral catheters and their balloons: drainage, anchorage, dilation, and hemostasis. *J Endourol.* 1993; 7: 89-92
12. Nacey J, Delahunt B. The evolution and development of the urinary catheter. *Aust N Z J Surg.* 1993; 63: 815-819
13. Karchmer TB, Giannetta ET, Muto CA, Strain BA, Farr BM. A randomized crossover study of silver-coated urinary catheters in hospitalized patients. *Arch Intern Med.* 2000; 160:3294-3298
14. Mattelaer, Johan, Billiet, Ignace. Catheters and sounds: The history of bladder catheterisation. *Paraplegia.* 1995; 33:429-433
15. Moog FP, Karenberg A, Moll F. The catheter and its use from Hippocrates to Galen. *J Urol.* 2005; 174:1196–1198
16. Moog FP, Karenberg A, Moll F. The catheter and its use in Late Antiquity and the early Middle Ages. *J Urol.* 2005; 174:439–441
17. Tatem AJ, Klaassen Z, Lewis RW, Terris MK. Frederick Eugene Basil Foley: his life and innovations. *Urology.* 2013; 81:927–931
18. Standring S. *Gray's anatomy.* 40th ed. Edinburgh: Churchill Livingstone; 2008
19. Kohler TS, Yadven M, Manvar A. The length of the male urethra. *Int Braz J Urol.* 2008; 34:451–456
20. Davis GG. *Applied anatomy: the construction of the human body.* Philadelphia: JB Lippincott; 1913

21. Wieczorek AP, Wozniak MM, Stankiewicz A. 3-D high-frequency endo- vaginal ultrasound of female urethral complex and assessment of inter- observer reliability. *Eur J Radiol.* 2012; 81:7-12
22. Uehling DT. The normal caliber of the adult female urethra. *J Urol.* 1978; 120:176–177
23. Wein AJ, Kavoussi LR, Partin AW, Peters CA. *Campbell-Walsh Urology.* 11th ed. Philadelphia: Elsevier; 2016
24. Bullock TL, Brandes SB. Adult anterior urethral strictures: a national practice patterns survey of board certified urologists in the United States. *J Urol.* 2007; 177:685–690
25. Smith L. Which catheter? Criteria for selection of urinary catheters for children. *Paediatr Nurs.* 2003; 15:14-18
26. Jahn P, Beutner K, Langer G. Types of indwelling urinary catheters for long-term bladder drainage in adults. *Cochrane Database Syst Rev.* 2018; 10:47-77
27. Newman DK. The indwelling urinary catheter: Principles for best practice. *J Wound Ostomy Contenance Nurs.* 2007; 34:655-661
28. Villanueva C, Hossain SG, Nelson CA. Silicone catheters may be superior to latex catheters in difficult urethral catheterization after urethral dilation. *J Endourol.* 2011; 25:841–844
29. Siddiq DM, Darouiche RO. New strategies to prevent catheter-associated urinary tract infections. *Nat Rev Urol.* 2012; 9:305–314.
30. Wilson W, Taubert KA, Gewitz M, Lockhart PB, Baddour LM, Levison M, et al. Prevention of infective endocarditis: guidelines from the American Heart Association: a guideline from the American Heart Association Rheumatic Fever, Endocarditis, and Kawasaki Disease Committee, Council on Cardiovascular Disease in the Young, and the Council on Clinical Cardiology, Council on Cardiovascular Surgery and Anesthesia, and the Quality of Care and Outcomes Research Interdisciplinary Working Group. *Circulation.* 2007; 116:1736–1754
31. Haines JS, Grabstald H. Xylocaine; a new topical anesthetic in urology. *J Urol.* 1949; 62:901

32. Ouellette RD, Blute R, Jaffee S. Plasma concentrations of lidocaine resulting from instillation of lidocaine jelly into genitourinary tract prior to cystoscopy. *Urology*. 1985; 25:490–491
33. Sundaram MB. Seizures after intraurethral instillation of lidocaine. *CMAJ* 1987; 137:219–220
34. McFarlane N, Denstedt J, Ganapathy S, Razvi H. Randomized trial of 10 mL and 20 mL of 2% intraurethral lidocaine gel and placebo in men undergoing flexible cystoscopy. *J Endourol*. 2001; 15:541–544
35. Thompson TJ, Thompson N, O'Brien A, Young MR, McCleane G. To determine whether the temperature of 2% lignocaine gel affects the initial discomfort which may be associated with its instillation into the male urethra. *BJU Int*. 1999; 84:1035–1037
36. Choong S, Whitfield HN, Meganathan V. A prospective, randomized, double-blind study comparing lignocaine gel and plain lubricating gel in relieving pain during flexible cystoscopy. *Br J Urol*. 1997; 80:69–71.
37. Sharpe SJ, Mann FA, Wiedmeyer CE, et al. Optimal filling solution for silicone Foley catheter balloons. *Can Vet J*. 2011; 52:1111–1114
38. Nyman MA, Schwenk NM, Silverstein MD. Management of urinary retention: rapid versus gradual decompression and risk of complications. *Mayo Clin Proc*. 1997; 72:951–956
39. Richards MJ, Edwards JR, Culver DH, Gaynes RP. Nosocomial infections in combined medical-surgical intensive care units in the United States. *Infect Control Hosp Epidemiol*. 2000; 21:510–515
40. Dudeck MA, Horan TC, Peterson KD, Allen-Bridson K, Morrell G, Pollock DA, et al. National Healthcare Safety Network (NHSN) report, data summary for 2009, device-associated module. *Am J Infect Control*. 2011; 39:349–367
41. Maki DG, Tambyah PA. Engineering out the risk for infection with urinary catheters. *Emerg Infect Dis*. 2001; 7:342–347

42. Darouiche RO, Al Mohajer M, Siddiq DM. A short versus long course of antibiotics for catheter-associated urinary tract infections in patients with spinal cord injury: a randomized controlled non-inferiority trial. *Arch Phys Med Rehabil.* 2014; 95:290–296
43. Wolf JS, Bennett CJ, Dmochowski RR, Hollenbeck BK, Pearle MS, Schaeffer AJ. Best practice policy statement on urologic surgery antimicrobial prophylaxis. *J Urol.* 2008;179: 1379–1390
44. Hollingsworth JM, Rogers MA, Krein SL, Hickner A, Kuhn L, Cheng A, et al. Determining the non-infectious complications of indwelling urethral catheters: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Ann Intern Med.* 2013; 159:401–410
45. Chung E, So K. In vitro analysis of balloon cuffing phenomenon: inherent biophysical properties of catheter material or mechanics of catheter balloon deflation? *Surg Innov.* 2012; 19:175–180
46. Gonzalgo ML, Walsh PC. Balloon cuffing and management of the entrapped Foley catheter. *Urology.* 2003; 61:825–827
47. Stickler DJ, Feneley RC. The encrustation and blockage of long-term indwelling bladder catheters: a way forward in prevention and control. *Spinal Cord.* 2010; 48:784–790
48. Lang EK, Nguyen QD, Zhang K, Smith MH. Missed iatrogenic partial disruption of the male urethra, caused by catheterization. *Int Braz J Urol.* 2012; 38:426–427
49. Wu AK, Blaschko SD, Garcia M, McAninch JW, Aaronson DS. Safer urethral catheters: how study of catheter balloon pressure and force can guide design. *BJU Int.* 2012; 109:1110–1114
50. Kashefi C, Messer K, Barden R, Sexton C, Parsons JK. Incidence and prevention of iatrogenic urethral injuries. *J Urol.* 2008; 179:2254–2258
51. Chung PH, Wong CW, Lai CK, Siu HK, Tsang DN, Yeung KY, et al. A prospective interventional study to examine the effect of a silver alloy and hydrogel-coated catheter on the incidence of catheter-associated urinary tract infection. *Hong Kong Med J.* 2017; 23:239-245

52. Lederer JW, Jarvis WR, Thomas L, Ritter J. Multicenter Cohort Study to Assess the Impact of a Silver-Alloy and Hydrogel-Coated Urinary Catheter on Symptomatic Catheter-Associated Urinary Tract Infections. *J Wound Ostomy Continence Nurs.* 2014; 41:473–480
53. Roe D, Karandikar B, Gibbins B. Antimicrobial surface functionalization of plastic catheters by silver nanoparticles. *Journal of Antimicrobial Chemotherapy.* 2008; 4:869–876
54. Siroky MB, Oates RD, Babayan RK. *Handbook of Urology: Diagnosis and Therapy.* 3rd ed. Philadelphia: Lippincott Williams and Wilkins; 2004
55. Favre HA, Powell WH. *Nomenclature of Organic Chemistry: IUPAC Recommendations and Preferred Names 2013.* Cambridge: The Royal Society of Chemistry; 2014
56. Hipler UC, Elsner P. *Biofunctional Textiles and the Skin.* *Curr Probl Dermatol.* Basel, Karger. 2006; 33:17-34
57. Marx J, Hockberger R, Walls R. *Rosen's Emergency Medicine: Concepts and Clinical Practice.* 8th ed. Philadelphia: Elsevier; 2016
58. Gill N, Maggie JW, Amber DR, Nikki S, Marta OS, Jo CD. Dressings and topical agents for treating venous leg ulcers. *Cochrane Database Syst Rev.* 2018; 6: CD012583
59. Dissemond J, Böttrich JG, Braunwarth H, Hilt J, Wilken P, Münter KC et al. Evidence for silver in wound care - meta-analysis of clinical studies from 2000-2015. *Journal der Deutschen Dermatologischen Gesellschaft.* 2017; 15: 524–535
60. Tokmaji G, Vermeulen H, Müller MCA, Kwakman PHS, Schultz MJ, Zaat SAJ. Silver coated endotracheal tubes for prevention of ventilator-associated pneumonia in critically ill patients. *Cochrane Database Syst Rev.* 2011; 7:CD009201
61. National Centre for Biotechnology Information. PubChem Database. Formamide, CID=713, <https://pubchem.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/compound/Formamide> (accessed on Sept. 14, 2019).

62. Houston IB. Pus Cell and Bacterial Counts in the Diagnosis of Urinary Tract Infections in Childhood. *Arch Dis Child*. 1963; 38:600–605
63. Thibon P, Leroyer R, Fabry J. Randomized Multi-Centre Trial of the Effects of a Catheter Coated with Hydrogel and Silver Salts on the Incidence of Hospital-Acquired Urinary Tract Infections. *Journal of Hospital Infection*. 2000; 45:117–124
64. Tambyah PA, Dennis GM. Catheter-Associated Urinary Tract Infection Is Rarely Symptomatic. *Archives of Internal Medicine*. 2000; 160:678-682

11. ANNEXURE I – ETHICAL CLEARANCE CERTIFICATE

12. ANNEXURE II – SAMPLE INFORMED CONSENT FORM:

TITLE OF THE PROJECT : COMPARATIVE STUDY OF SILVER COATED URINARY CATHETER VS CONVENTIONAL LATEX CATHETER IN PREVENTION OF NOSOCOMIAL CATHETER ASSOCIATED URINARY TRACT INFECTION

PURPOSE OF RESEARCH:

I have been informed that this study is conducted to compare and evaluate the efficacy of silver coated urinary catheter with conventional latex urinary catheter in prevention/reduction of catheter associated urinary tract infection.

PROCEDURE:

I am aware that in addition to routine care received I will be asked series of questions by the investigator. I have been asked to undergo the necessary investigations and treatment, which will help the investigator in this study.

Patients who met the inclusion criteria were randomly assigned a Study group (Group A) or Control group (Group B).

RISK AND DISCOMFORTS:

I understand that I may experience some pain and discomforts during the examination or during my treatment. This is mainly the result of my condition and the procedures of this study are not expected to exaggerate these feelings which are associated with the usual course of treatment.

BENEFITS:

I understand that my participation in the study will help to predict to evaluate the efficacy of placement of drains in the thyroid surgeries and to compare it without placing drains.

CONFIDENTIALITY:

I understand that the medical information produced by this study will become a part of hospital records and will be subject to the confidentiality. Information of sensitive personal nature will not be part of the medical record, but will be stored in the investigations research file.

If the data are used for publication in the medical literature or for teaching purpose, no name will be used and other identifiers such as photographs will be used only with special written permission. I understand that I may see the photograph before giving the permission.

REQUEST FOR MORE INFORMATION:

I understand that I may ask more questions about the study to **Dr. XXX** in the Department of General Surgery who will be available to answer my questions or concerns. I understand that I will be informed of any significant new findings discovered during the course of the study, which might influence my continued participation. A copy of this consent form will be given to me to keep for careful reading.

REFUSAL FOR WITHDRAWAL OF PARTICIPATION:

I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I may refuse to participate or may withdraw consent and discontinue participation in the study at any time without prejudice. I also understand that **Dr. XXX** may terminate my participation in the study after he has explained the reasons for doing so.

INJURY STATEMENT:

I understand that in the unlikely event of injury to me resulting directly from my participation in this study, if such injury were reported promptly, the appropriate treatment would be available to me. But no further compensation would be provided by the hospital. I understand that by my agreements to participate in this study and not waiving any of my legal rights.

I have explained to _____ the purpose of the research, the procedures required and the possible risks to the best of my ability.

Dr.XXX
(Investigator)

Date

STUDY SUBJECT CONSENT STATEMENT:

I confirm that **Dr. XXX** has explained to me the purpose of research, the study procedure, that I will undergo and the possible discomforts as well as benefits that I may experience in my own language. I have been explained all the above in detail in my own language and I understand the same. Therefore, I agree to give consent to participate as a subject in this research project.

(Participant)

Date

(Witness to signature)

Date

13. ANNEXURE III – PROFORMA

SL NO

NAME

AGE

IP NO

SEX

UNIT

RELIGION

DOA

OCCUPATION

WARD

ADDRESS

DOD

SOCIO-ECONOMIC STATUS

Complaints:

HISTORY OF PRESENT ILLNESS

SYSTEMIC SYMPTOMS

PAST HISTORY:

PERSONAL HISTORY:

GENERAL PHYSICAL EXAMINATION

BUILT: WELL/MODERATE/POOR

NOURISHMENT: WELL/MODERATE/POOR

[BMI=]

PALLOR

ICTERUS

CYANOSIS

CLUBBING

PEDAL EDEMA

GENERAL LYMPHADENOPATHY

VITAL DATA:

TEMPERATURE:

PULSE

RESPIRATORY RATE

BLOOD PRESSURE:

SYSTEMIC EXAMINATION

PER ABDOMEN:

RESPIRATORY SYSTEM

CARDIOVASCULAR SYSTEM

CENTRAL NERVOUS SYSTEM

PER RECTAL EXAMINATION

CLINICAL DIAGNOSIS:

INDICATION FOR CATHETERISATION

TYPE OF CATHETER

LABORATORY TESTS

HB%

TOTAL COUNT

DIFFERENTIAL COUNT

N/L/E/B/M:

URINE ROUTINE:	DAY 1	DAY 3	DAY 7
----------------	-------	-------	-------

Pus cells-

URINE CULTURE AND SENSITIVITY:	DAY 1	DAY 3	DAY 7
--------------------------------	-------	-------	-------

Organisms isolated-

Culture sensitivity pattern-

DATE OF URINARY CATHETER REMOVAL

URINARY CATHETER TIP CULTURE AND SENSITIVITY

RBS

B. UREA

S. CREATININE

HIV

HBsAg

CHEST X RAY